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COURSE NAME:
CRITICAL THINKING

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1. INTRODUCTION

The capacity to think critically is defined as the ability to examine information with an open mind. It involves evaluating the evidence, identifying assumptions, and drawing conclusions. Critical thinking is essential for making informed decisions in all aspects of life, including education, employment, and citizenship.

Globalization is the process of increasing interconnectedness between countries and cultures. It has had a profound impact on Cambodia, both positive and negative. On the one hand, globalization has helped to improve the country's economy and standard of living. On the other hand, it has also led to challenges such as environmental degradation and cultural erosion.

In the context of globalization, critical thinking is more important than ever for Cambodians. It can help them to understand the challenges and opportunities of globalization, and to make informed decisions about their future. Critical thinking can also help Cambodians to protect their culture and identity from the negative impacts of globalization.

Critical thinking is comprised of several distinct parts. Some of the most important include: *Analysis* is the skill of examining data to reveal its underlying structure and uncovering hidden relationships. *Evaluation*: Knowing how to evaluate the reliability of sources and separate reality from speculation. *Inference*: The ability to draw conclusions based on the evidence. *Problem-solving*: Ability to diagnose issues and find workable solutions. *Creativity* is the capacity for original thought and the generation of innovative solutions to problems.

Critical thinking is not something that people are born with. It is a skill that needs to be taught and learned. There are many different ways to teach critical thinking, but some of the most effective methods include: *Problem-based learning*: This involves giving students real-world problems to solve. *Critical thinking workshops*: These workshops provide students with the opportunity to learn about the different elements of critical thinking and to practice their skills. *Critical thinking exercises*: These exercises can be used to help students develop their critical thinking skills.

There are some challenges to teaching critical thinking in Cambodia. One challenge is that the traditional Cambodian education system does not focus on critical thinking. Another challenge is that many Cambodian teachers lack the training and skills necessary to teach critical thinking.

Critical thinking is an essential skill for Cambodians in the 21st century. It can help them to understand the challenges and opportunities of globalization, and to make informed decisions about their future. Critical thinking can also help Cambodians to protect their culture and identity from the negative impacts of globalization.

The future of critical thinking in Cambodia is bright. There is a growing awareness of the importance of critical thinking, and there are a number of initiatives underway to promote critical thinking education. As critical thinking becomes more widely taught and learned, it will help to ensure that Cambodia has a well-informed and engaged citizenry that is capable of making wise decisions about the future of the country.

There is a role to play in promoting critical thinking in Cambodia. Teachers or learners can do this by:

- Supporting critical thinking education initiatives.

- Encouraging our children and students to develop critical thinking skills.
- Modeling critical thinking ourselves.

By working together, people can help to ensure that Cambodia has a future that is bright and prosperous.

2. CRITICAL THINKING

2.1. Summary of the topic. Describing course concepts.

Critical thinking refers to the cognitive capacity to engage in clear and reasonable thought processes while evaluating and analyzing information. It involves evaluating the evidence, identifying assumptions, and drawing conclusions. Critical thinking is essential for making informed decisions in all aspects of life, including education, employment, and citizenship. The practice of critical thinking entails critiquing one's own mental processes with the goal of bettering them. Self-control, self-discipline, self-monitoring, and self-correction are hallmarks of the critical thinker (Paul, R., & Elder, L. 2019).

Here are some of the course concepts in a critical thinking course:

Evaluating evidence: This involves determining the quality of the evidence, its relevance to the claim, and its potential biases.

Identifying assumptions: This involves recognizing the unstated beliefs and premises that underlie an argument.

Drawing conclusions: This involves determining whether the conclusion of an argument follows logically from the evidence and assumptions.

Fallacies: These are errors in reasoning that can lead to false conclusions.

Problem-solving: This entails the process of systematically and logically identifying and resolving difficulties (Jain, H. 2023, March 23).

Creativity: This involves thinking outside the box and coming up with new ideas.

A critical thinking course will typically cover these concepts in detail and provide students, or researchers with opportunities to practice their critical thinking skills. The

course may also include readings, assignments, and discussions that help students to develop their critical thinking skills.

The development of critical thinking abilities has many advantages:

Improved decision-making: Critical thinking can help learners/researchers to make better decisions about your life.

Increased creativity: Critical thinking can help learners/researchers to be more creative and innovative.

Greater resilience: Critical thinking can help learners/researchers to be more resilient in the face of challenges.

Enhanced problem-solving skills: Critical thinking can help learners/researchers to solve problems more effectively.

Improved communication skills: Critical thinking can help learners/researchers to communicate your ideas more effectively.

2.2. Opinions and analysis of the course concepts.

2.2.1. Evaluating evidence

Evaluating evidence is an important part of critical thinking. It involves determining the quality of the evidence, its relevance to the claim, and its potential biases.

Here are some questions to ask when evaluating evidence:

- a. Is the evidence reliable? This means that it comes from a credible source and has been properly documented.
- b. Is the evidence relevant? This means that it directly supports the claim that is being made.

- c. Is the evidence sufficient? This means that there is enough evidence to support the claim.
- d. Is the evidence biased? This means that it is influenced by the personal beliefs or opinions of the source.
- e. Is the evidence up-to-date? This means that it is recent and reflects the latest information on the topic.

The consideration of evidentiary context is of equal significance (Drew, C. August 20, 2023). For example, if the evidence is from a study, learners/researchers need to consider the methods used in the study and the potential for bias.

Evaluating evidence is a complex process, but it is an essential skill for critical thinking. By carefully evaluating the evidence, learners/researchers can be more confident in the conclusions that learners/researchers draw.

Here are some additional tips for evaluating evidence:

- Be aware of their own biases. Everyone has biases, so it is important to be aware of them when evaluating evidence.
- Get multiple sources of evidence. It is always best to get multiple sources of evidence before drawing a conclusion.
- Be skeptical of evidence that is not supported by other sources. If learners/researchers only find one source of evidence for a claim, be skeptical of that claim.
- Consider the context of the evidence. Where did the evidence come from? Who created it? What is the purpose of the evidence?

- Don't be afraid to ask questions. If learners/researchers are not sure about the quality of the evidence, ask questions.

2.2.2. Identifying assumptions

Identifying assumptions is an important part of critical thinking. Assumptions are the unstated beliefs and premises that underlie an argument. They are often implicit, meaning that they are not explicitly stated. However, they can be just as important as the stated premises in determining the validity of an argument.

Here are some tips for identifying assumptions:

- a. Look for words and phrases that suggest an assumption. These words and phrases can include "assume," "infer," "it follows that," and "must be."
- b. Consider the context of the argument. What is the speaker or writer trying to prove? What are they leaving out?
- c. Be skeptical of claims that seem too good to be true. If an argument seems to make a claim without providing any evidence, it is likely that an assumption is being made.
- d. Ask questions. When learners/researchers are reading or listening to an argument, ask themselves what assumptions are being made.

Here are some examples of assumptions:

- ✓ "The earth is round." This is an assumption that most people make, but it is not explicitly stated.
- ✓ "If you study hard, you will get good grades." This assumption is implicit in the statement.

- ✓ "Everyone should vote." This assumption is based on the belief that voting is important.
- ✓ By identifying assumptions, learners/researchers can better understand the arguments that they are presented with. They can also be more critical of the claims that are made.

some additional tips for identifying assumptions:

- Be aware of their own biases. Everyone has biases, so it is important to be aware of them when identifying assumptions.
- Get multiple perspectives. It is always best to get multiple perspectives on an argument before drawing a conclusion.
- Don't be afraid to ask questions. If learners/researchers are not sure about an assumption, ask questions.

2.2.3. Drawing conclusions

Drawing conclusions is an important part of critical thinking. It involves determining whether the conclusion of an argument follows logically from the evidence and assumptions.

Here are some tips for drawing conclusions:

- a. Make sure that the conclusion follows from the evidence. The conclusion should be supported by the evidence that is presented.
- b. Consider all of the evidence, not just the evidence that supports their conclusion. It is important to be aware of all of the evidence, even if it does not support their conclusion.

- c. Be aware of their own biases. Everyone has biases, so it is important to be aware of them when drawing conclusions.
- d. Get multiple perspectives. It is always best to get multiple perspectives on an argument before drawing a conclusion.
- e. Don't be afraid to ask questions. If learners/researchers are not sure about the conclusion, ask questions.

Here are some examples of how to draw conclusions:

- ✓ If the evidence shows that all swans that have been observed are white, then it is reasonable to conclude that all swans are white.
- ✓ If the evidence shows that smoking causes cancer, then it is reasonable to conclude that smoking is a harmful habit.
- ✓ If the evidence shows that there is no evidence of intelligent life on other planets, then it is reasonable to conclude that intelligent life on other planets is unlikely.

By following these tips, learners/researchers can improve their skills in drawing conclusions and become a more critical thinker.

Here are some common mistakes to avoid when drawing conclusions:

- Given that the data is supportive, it may be assumed that the conclusion is valid (Drew, C. August 20, 2023). The conclusion should follow from the evidence, but it is not always the case that the conclusion is true.
- Ignoring evidence that does not support learner's/researchers' conclusion. It is important to consider all of the evidence, even if it does not support their conclusion.

- Allowing their biases to influence their conclusions. Everyone has biases, so it is important to be aware of them and to try to avoid letting them influence their conclusions.
- Drawing conclusions without enough evidence. It is important to have enough evidence to support your conclusions.
- Drawing conclusions too quickly. It is vital to provide sufficient time for the comprehensive evaluation of all available facts prior to formulating a decision.

By avoiding these mistakes, learners/ researchers can improve your skills in drawing conclusions and become a more critical thinker.

2.2.4. Fallacies

A fallacy refers to a logical flaw in the process of reasoning, which has the potential to result in an inaccurate or incorrect conclusion. Fallacies are prevalent not just in casual daily arguments but also in more structured formal discussions and debates (R. 2023, February 13).

There are many different types of fallacies, but some of the most common include:

- a. Ad hominem: This fallacy attacks the person making the argument, rather than the argument itself. For example, saying "You're wrong because you're biased" is an ad hominem fallacy.
- b. Appeal to authority: This fallacy relies on the authority of an expert to support a claim. For example, saying "Einstein said it, so it must be true" is an appeal to authority fallacy.

- c. Bandwagon: This fallacy assumes that something is true because many people believe it. For example, saying "Everyone is doing it, so it must be okay" is a bandwagon fallacy.
- d. False cause: This fallacy assumes that one event causes another event, when there is no evidence to support this claim. For example, saying "I ate a banana and then I got a good grade on my test, so the banana must have caused me to do well" is a false cause fallacy.
- e. Straw man: This fallacy distorts the argument of the other person in order to make it easier to attack. For example, saying "You're saying that we should never eat meat, but that's not what I'm saying at all" is a straw man fallacy.

Fallacies can be difficult to spot, but it is important to be aware of them so that learners/researchers can avoid being persuaded by them. Here are some tips for spotting fallacies:

- ✓ Be aware of the common types of fallacies. The more learners/researchers know about fallacies, the easier it will be to spot them.
- ✓ Pay attention to the structure of the argument. Fallacious arguments often have a flawed structure.
- ✓ Consider the evidence. Does the evidence support the conclusion?
- ✓ Be skeptical of claims that seem too good to be true. Fallacious arguments often make claims that are not supported by evidence.
- ✓ Ask questions. If learners/researchers are not sure about an argument, ask questions.

By following these tips, learners/researchers can improve your skills in spotting fallacies and become a more critical thinker.

Here are some additional tips for avoiding fallacies:

- Be aware of their own biases. Everyone has biases, so it is important to be aware of them and to try to avoid letting them influence your thinking.
- Get multiple perspectives. It is always best to get multiple perspectives on an argument before forming their own opinion.
- Don't be afraid to ask questions. If learners/researchers are not sure about something, ask questions.

By following these tips, learners/researchers can improve your skills in avoiding fallacies and become a more critical thinker.

2.2.5. Problem-solving

Problem-solving is a critical thinking skill that involves identifying a problem, brainstorming possible solutions, and evaluating the feasibility of each solution. It is an essential skill for making informed decisions and taking effective action.

Here are some of the steps involved in problem-solving using critical thinking:

- a. Identify the problem. What is the problem that learners/researchers are trying to solve? What are the symptoms of the problem? What are the underlying causes of the problem?
- b. Brainstorm possible solutions. After the identification of the issue, learners or researchers should engage in a process of generating a multitude of potential answers via brainstorming. At this level, it is not necessary to

concern oneself with the practicality or feasibility of the proposed solutions.

The primary objective is to generate a substantial number of ideas.

- c. Evaluate the solutions. Once they have a list of possible solutions, evaluate each one. Consider the pros and cons of each solution, as well as the feasibility of each solution.
- d. Choose the best solution. Once they have evaluated the solutions, choose the best solution for them. The best solution may not be the most obvious solution. It may be the solution that is most feasible or the solution that has the fewest drawbacks.
- e. Implement the solution. Once learners/researchers have chosen the best solution, implement it. This may need implementing measures or effecting modifications (DM_Theory - BusinessThink, n.d.).
- f. Evaluate the results. Once they have implemented the solution, evaluate the results. Did the solution solve the problem? If not, they may need to go back to step b and brainstorm new solutions.

Problem-solving is an iterative process. It may take several tries to find the best solution to a problem. However, by using critical thinking skills, learners/researchers can improve their ability to identify problems, brainstorm solutions, and evaluate the results.

Here are some tips for using critical thinking skills to solve problems:

- ✓ Be open-minded. Don't rule out any solutions without considering them carefully.
- ✓ Be willing to ask for help. If they are stuck, don't be afraid to ask for help from others.

- ✓ Be persistent. Don't give up easily. Keep trying until they find a solution that works.

By following these tips, learners/researchers can improve your ability to use critical thinking skills to solve problems.

2.2.6. Creativity

Creativity and critical thinking are often seen as two opposing ways of thinking. However, they are actually complementary skills that can be used together to solve problems and make decisions.

Creativity is the ability to generate new ideas and solutions. It involves thinking outside the box and coming up with new perspectives. Critical thinking is the ability to evaluate information and arguments. It involves analyzing evidence, identifying assumptions, and drawing conclusions.

When used together, creativity and critical thinking can help learners/researchers to:

- a. *Solve problems more effectively.* When they are faced with a problem, they can use their creativity to generate new solutions. Then, they can use your critical thinking skills to evaluate these solutions and choose the best one.
- b. *Make better decisions.* When they are making a decision, they can use their creativity to generate different options. Then, they can use your critical thinking skills to evaluate these options and choose the best one for them.
- c. *Be more innovative.* Creativity can help them to come up with new ideas and solutions that have not been thought of before. Critical thinking can help

them to evaluate these ideas and solutions and determine if they are feasible.

- d. *Be more open-minded.* Creativity can help learners/researchers to see things from different perspectives. Critical thinking can help them to evaluate these perspectives and determine which one is the most accurate.

So, while creativity and critical thinking may seem like opposites, they are actually two sides of the same coin. When used together, they can help learners/researchers to become a more effective thinker and problem solver.

Here are some examples of how creativity and critical thinking can be used together:

- ✓ A scientist is trying to develop a new drug to treat a disease. They use their creativity to generate different possible drug compounds. Then, they use their critical thinking skills to evaluate these compounds and choose the one that is most likely to be effective.
- ✓ A businessperson is trying to come up with a new marketing campaign. They use their creativity to generate different possible ideas. Then, they use their critical thinking skills to evaluate these ideas and choose the one that is most likely to be successful.
- ✓ A student is trying to write a research paper. They use their creativity to generate different possible research questions. Then, they use their critical thinking skills to evaluate these questions and choose the one that is most likely to lead to a successful paper.

By using creativity and critical thinking together, learners/researchers can become a more effective thinker and problem solver. They can also become more innovative and open-minded.

2.3. How to apply the knowledge to the life, work and community

Here are some ways to apply critical thinking knowledge to life, work, and community:

2.3.1. In life:

When making decisions: Use critical thinking skills to evaluate the information they have, identify the pros and cons of each option, and make the best decision for them.

When solving problems: Use critical thinking skills to identify the problem, brainstorm possible solutions, and evaluate the feasibility of each solution.

When evaluating information: Use critical thinking skills to assess the credibility of the source, the relevance of the information, and the potential biases.

When being persuaded: Use critical thinking skills to identify the arguments being made, evaluate the evidence, and identify any fallacies.

When being creative: Use critical thinking skills to generate new ideas and solutions, and to evaluate these ideas and solutions.

2.3.2. In work:

When gathering information: Use critical thinking skills to evaluate the quality of the information, identify the potential biases, and determine if the information is relevant to their needs.

When making decisions: Use critical thinking skills to evaluate the options available to them, identify the risks and benefits of each option, and make the best decision for their company.

When solving problems: Use critical thinking skills to identify the problem, brainstorm possible solutions, and evaluate the feasibility of each solution.

When communicating with others: Use critical thinking skills to assess the credibility of the information, identify any potential biases, and evaluate the arguments being made.

When being creative: Use critical thinking skills to generate new ideas and solutions, and to evaluate these ideas and solutions.

By raising the profile of critical thinking in knowledge management, companies may take their strategies and employee education in new directions (Indrašienė, V., Jegelevičienė, V., Merfeldaitė, O., Penkauskienė, D., Pivorienė, J., Railienė, A., ... & Valavičienė, N. 2021).

2.3.3. In community:

When participating in civic activities: Use critical thinking skills to evaluate the information they are given, identify the potential biases, and make informed decisions about the issues.

When volunteering: Use critical thinking skills to identify the needs of the community, develop effective solutions, and evaluate the impact of their work.

When advocating for change: Use critical thinking skills to identify the problem, develop a plan for change, and evaluate the effectiveness of their efforts.

When resolving conflict: Use critical thinking skills to identify the underlying issues, brainstorm possible solutions, and evaluate the feasibility of each solution.

When being creative: Use critical thinking skills to generate new ideas and solutions to address community problems.

By applying critical thinking knowledge to their life, work, and community, they can make better decisions, solve problems more effectively, and be more creative. They can also be more informed and engaged in civic activities, and make a positive impact on the world around them.

2.4. Personal Experiences

Some examples of how critical thinking can be used in my everyday life:

Making decisions: When I'm making a decision, it is important to consider all of the information available to me. They should also be aware of their own biases and how they might affect my decision-making.

Solving problems: When I am faced with a problem, it is important to identify the problem and brainstorm possible solutions. I should then evaluate each solution and choose the one that is most likely to be successful.

Evaluating information: When I am presented with new information, it is important to evaluate its source and credibility. I should also be aware of potential biases in the information.

Being persuaded: When I being persuaded by someone, it is important to be aware of the arguments being made. I should also be critical of the evidence that is presented.

It is possible to develop one's capacity for critical thinking via study and exercise. There are many resources available to help me learn critical thinking skills, such as books, articles, and online courses.

2.5. Case examples to demonstrate the concepts of critical thinking

here are some case examples to demonstrate the concepts of critical thinking:

- a. *A doctor is trying to diagnose a patient.* The doctor must carefully consider all of the symptoms, the patient's medical history, and the results of any tests. The doctor must also be aware of their own biases and how they might affect their diagnosis.
- b. *A lawyer is preparing for a trial.* The lawyer must carefully consider the evidence, the law, and the arguments of the opposing side. The lawyer must also be aware of any potential biases in the evidence or the law.
- c. *A student is writing a research paper.* The student must carefully consider the sources they are using, the arguments they are making, and the evidence they are presenting. The student must also be aware of any potential biases in the sources or the evidence.
- d. *A voter is deciding who to vote for in an election.* The voter must carefully consider the candidates' positions on the issues, their qualifications, and their experience. The voter must also be aware of any potential biases in the candidates' statements or the media coverage of the election.
- e. *A consumer is deciding whether to buy a product.* The consumer must carefully consider the product's features, price, and reviews. The consumer

must also be aware of any potential biases in the reviews or the advertising for the product.

These are just a few examples of how critical thinking can be used in everyday life. By using critical thinking skills, learners/researcher can make better decisions, solve problems more effectively, and be more informed and engaged in the world around them.

3. CONCLUSION

In summary, critical thinking can be a multidimensional and intricate talent that enables individuals to assess information, make informed judgments, and effectively address challenges. It is an essential skill for anyone who wants to be an informed and engaged citizen. Critical thinking could have discussed the following:

- a. The different types of critical thinking skills, such as evaluating evidence, identifying assumptions, and drawing conclusions
- b. The importance of critical thinking in everyday life, such as when making decisions, solving problems, and being persuaded,
- c. The challenges of critical thinking include our own biases and the prevalence of misinformation.
- d. The ways to improve critical thinking skills, such as by practicing, being open-minded, and being aware of our own biases.

The conclusion could have summarized the main points and emphasized the importance of critical thinking in learners and researchers' everyday lives. It could have also called the reader to action, encouraging them to use their critical thinking skills to make a difference in the world.

Critical thinking is a skill that can be learned and improved with practice. By learning to think critically, learners and researchers can make better decisions, solve problems more effectively, and be more informed and engaged citizens. They can also help create a more just and equitable world.

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